

Notepad++

GUI Change Detection tool

Comparing the GUI menu and settings panels from versions 8.4.5 to 8.4.6

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Notepad ++ v8.4.6 with v8.4.5

<https://github.com/notepad-plus-plus/notepad-plus-plus/compare/v8.4.5...v8.4.6>

Style Configurator Panel

The “Change History margin” list element was added.

This specific state has changed.

AUTOMATIC HIGHLIGHT OF GUI CHANGES

File Menu

“Close More” was renamed to “Close Multiple Documents”

This specific state has changed.

AUTOMATIC HIGHLIGHT OF GUI CHANGES

Edit - Copy to Clipboard Sub-Menu

All Copy to Clipboard sub-menu elements were renamed.

This specific state has changed.

AUTOMATIC HIGHLIGHT OF GUI CHANGES

View - Tab Sub-Menu

The view menu was detected as a specific state with changes.

Then, because the abstract action uses the state identifier, this “Tab” Sub-Menu is detected as a new action-state added in v8.4.6.

And as a removed action-state in v8.4.5.

New added “Apply Color” elements into Tab sub-menu

v8.4.6 ADDED ACTION-STATE

v8.4.5 REMOVED ACTION-STATE

